

Synthetic, spectral and biological activities of binuclear imidazolate-bridged complexes as Cu,Zn-SOD models possessing tris(2-aminoethyl)amine and amino acid derived ligands

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Abstract : Synthetic, spectral and superoxide dismutase activities of the imidazolate-bridged binuclear copper(II)-zinc(II) complexes viz. $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$; $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 2$; $[(L^2)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 3$, derived from (*E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)acetic acid (H_2L); (*S,E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)propanoic acid (H_2L^1); (*R*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)-3-methylbutanoic acid (H_2L^2); tren = tris(2-aminoethyl)amine, Im = imidazolate ion, have been achieved. Magnetic moment values of hetero-binuclear complexes indicate that the imidazolate group can mediate antiferromagnetic interactions ($S = 1/2$) state. X-band EPR spectra of the complexes at different pH values in frozen solution showed that the metal complexes was stable in the pH range 6.50–11.00. Schiff base ligands (H_2L - H_2L^2) were synthesized by the condensation of equimolar (1 : 1) ratio of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde with glycine, alanine and valine, respectively, dissolved in ethanol. Biological (superoxide dismutase, antibacterial and antifungal) of these complexes have also been measured and compared with reported complexes.

Keywords : $Cu^{II}-Zn^{II}$ hetero-binuclear complexes, antibacterial, antiferromagnetic spin exchange, copper,zinc-superoxide dismutase, tridentate Schiff bases.

Introduction

Synthetic binuclear transition metal complexes provide models for metalloproteins active sites and lend insight towards the design of new catalysts. Interest in imidazolate-bridged binuclear metal complexes like bovine superoxide dismutase $[Cu^{II}-Im-Zn^{II}-SOD]$ has increased due to the involvement imidazolate ion as a bridging ligand between Cu^{II} ion and Zn^{II} ions (Scheme 1) in the Cu,Zn-superoxide dismutase enzyme^{1,2}. Superoxide dismutase (SOD)³ is known to have a histidine bridged copper(II)-zinc(II) active site occurs in each of the two identical subunits of the enzyme bovine erythrocyte superoxide dismutase (BESOD).

The deprotonated form of imidazole can serve as a bridging N_1, N_3 bi-dentate ligand for transition metal ions⁴. They involve the pairs of either identical or dissimilar metals bridged by a deprotonated imidazole type molecule. Consequently, a number of model compounds have been prepared. All these complexes exhibit antifer-

Scheme 1. The structure of active center of the copper-zinc-superoxide dismutase enzyme.

romagnetic spin exchange interactions. In recent years, application of SODs as therapeutic agent has attracted much attention, because of the harmful effect of the O_2^- ion *in vivo*^{5,6}. It is difficult, however, to employ SOD *in vivo* because it is readily cleared by the kidneys and is unable to enter cells because of its high molecular weights⁷.

Oberley and Buettner⁸ have reported that cancer cells

had less superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity than normal cells. As superoxide ion is toxic to cells; a defense mechanism must have been initiated by nature. We know that essentially all organisms, which use dioxygen and many that have to survive an oxygenated environment, contain at least one superoxide dismutase (SOD). The one which is pertinent to this article is a Cu, Zn protein found in cells that contain a nucleus (eukaryotic cells). X-Ray crystallographic studies^{1,2} have shown that the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions exist in distorted square planar and tetrahedral coordination environments, respectively. Copper, zinc-superoxide dismutase model shows bio catalytic activity towards the dismutation of superoxide anion according to the following equations⁹ :

Our research work is focusing on mimicking the active site of the Cu,Zn-superoxide dismutase (Cu,Zn-SOD) enzyme. This metalloenzyme is a dimeric protein with two identical subunits each containing one Cu^{II} ion and one Zn^{II} ion. It catalyzes the disproportionation of superoxide to hydrogen peroxide and dioxygen. With this reaction Cu,Zn-SOD reduces the risk of oxidative stress by removing the highly reactive superoxide. Former detailed mechanistic studies have demonstrated that the copper center is cyclically reduced and oxidized by superoxide; superoxide first reduce the Cu^{II} center of Cu,Zn-SOD to produce dioxygen (reaction (1)) and then another molecule of superoxide oxidizes the Cu^I center of Cu,Zn-SOD to produce hydrogen peroxide (reaction (2)).

Copper complexes have found possible medicinal uses in the treatment of many diseases including antibacterial, antifungal and anticancer¹⁰. It has been suggested that the anticancer activity of some copper(II) complexes may be based on their ability to inhibit DNA synthesis. Some metal complexes may be expected to be biologically active.

In order to model the active site of Cu,Zn-SOD enzyme, we synthesized and/or investigated, synthetic, spectral and biological activities of imidazolate-bridged hetero-binuclear copper(II)-zinc(II) complexes [(L)Cu-Im-

Zn(tren)]⁺ **1**; [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **2**; [(L²)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **3** using tris(2-aminoethyl)amine and tridentate ligands as a models of Cu,Zn-superoxide dismutase. Very few imidazolate-bridged hetero-binuclear copper(II)-zinc(II) complexes have been characterized as active site structural and functional models for [Cu₂,Cu₂-SOD] or [Cu₂,Zn₂-SOD] reported so far^{11,12}. Schiff base ligands (H₂L-H₂L²) were synthesized by the condensation of equimolar (1 : 1) ratio of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde with glycine, alanine and valine, respectively, dissolved in ethanol (Scheme 2). The H₂L-H₂L² is diprotic ligand typically act as tridentate, planar chelate ligand coordinating through phenolic-O, azomethine-N and carboxylate-O atom whereas tris(2-aminoethyl)amine behaves as a neutral tetradentate ligands.

Experimental

Materials used for synthesis :

Copper perchlorate hexahydrate and imidazole (Aldrich) were used as supplied. All the chemicals and solvents used were synthetic grade and used without further purification.

Cautions !

Perchlorate salts are potentially explosive and should be handled with great care and in only small quantities.

Instrumentation :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out with mercury(II) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units) as standard reference. EPR spectra were recorded with a Varian E-line Century Series Spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band with 100 kHz modulation frequency at room temperature and at 77 K. TCNE was used as field marker. The FT-IR spectra of the Schiff base ligands and their corresponding binuclear metal complexes were taken by the KBr technique, in the 400–4000 cm⁻¹ wave number range.

Superoxide dismutase activity :

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activities were evaluated using the following methods. The *in vitro* SOD activity was measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of superoxide radical (O₂⁻) and nitrobluetetrazolium chloride (NBT) as O₂⁻ scavenger¹³. In general, 400 μL sample to be as-

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Scheme 2. Proposed structures and synthetic procedure of the amino acid derived Schiff bases.

sayed was added to a solution containing 2.1 ml of 0.2 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 8.6) and 1 ml of 56 μM of alkaline DMSO solution was added while stirring. The absorbance was then monitored at 540 nm against a sample prepared under similar condition except NaOH was absent in DMSO. A unit of superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity is concentration of complex, which causes 50% inhibition of alkaline DMSO mediated reduction of NBT.

Antibacterial activity :

Filter paper disc diffusion plate method of Vinecent and Vinecent¹⁴ was used to test the *in vitro* antibacterial activities of synthesized complexes. The chosen strains were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The liquid medium containing the bacterial subcultures was autoclaved for 20 min at 121 °C and at 15 lb pressure before inoculation. The bacteria were then cultured for 24 h at 36 °C in an

incubator. Nutrient agar was poured into a plate and allowed to solidify. The test compounds (DMSO solutions) were added dropwise to a 10 mm diameter filter paper disc placed at the center of each agar plate. The plates were then kept at 5 °C for 1 h then transferred to an incubator maintained at 36 °C. The width of the growth inhibition zone around the disc was measured after 24 h incubation. Three replicates were made for each treatment.

Antifungal activity :

The antifungal activities of the compounds have been evaluated against *Aspergillus sp.*, *Penicillium sp.*, *Trichoderma sp.* and *Microsporium audonii* by the Radial Growth Method¹⁵ using czapek's agar medium. The compounds were added directly with the medium in 10, 20 and 30 mM concentrations. Controls were also run and three replicated were used in each case. The linear growth of the fungus was obtained by measuring the diameter of the fungal colony after four days. The amount of growth inhibition in all the replicates was calculated by the equation, % inhibition = $C - T/C \times 100$, where, C is the diameter of the fungal colony in the control plate and T is the diameter of the fungal colony in the test plate.

Preparations :

Synthesis of tridentate Schiff base ligands (H₂L-H₂L²):

Schiff base ligands (H₂L-H₂L²) were prepared by standard literature procedure^{16,17} and recrystallized from ethanol or methanol. Their purity was checked by elemental analysis. The Schiff base ligands (H₂L-H₂L²) was synthesized by refluxing 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (20 mmol, 4.02 g) with glycine (20 mmol, 1.50 g), alanine (20 mmol, 1.78 g) and valine (20 mmol, 2.32 g), respectively, in ethanol for 2-4 h; crystals appeared immediately after cooling to RT. The crystalline solid was filtered off, washed with ethanol, and dried in air and stored in CaCl₂ desiccators at room temperature. Yield : 90-95%.

Preparations of imidazole-bridged (Im) complexes [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ 1; [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ 2; [(L²)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ 3 :

Imidazole-bridged hetero binuclear complexes **1-3** were prepared by the published method^{18,19}. Their purity was checked by CHN analysis. The complexes were prepared by the following general procedure : Copper perchlorate

hexahydrate (2.0 mmol, 0.740 g), H₂L (2.0 mmol, 1.50 g), H₂L¹ (2.0 mmol, 1.78 g) and H₂L² (2.0 mmol, 2.32 g), respectively (Set A) was dissolve in 50% water-methanol mixed solvent. Similarly, zinc perchlorate hexahydrate (2.0 mmol, 0.744 g) with H₂L (2.0 mmol, 1.50 g), H₂L¹ (2.0 mmol, 1.78 g) and H₂L² (2.0 mmol, 2.32 g), respectively, was dissolve in 50% water-methanol, 50 : 50 v/v (Set B). Both sets (Set A and Set B) of solutions were stirred well separately and then mixed together and stirred again for half an hour. By adding 1 M NaOH solution, the pH of solutions was raised to 11. The solutions were left overnight at room temperature. The coloured crystalline products of [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **1**; [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **2**; [(L²)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **3** was isolated. The samples were collected by filtration, washed with ethanol and dried in anhydrous CaCl₂ desiccator. Yield : 80-90%. These hetero-binuclear complexes gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

The synthetic imidazole-bridged binuclear complexes were prepared by the following sequential routes without isolation of the mononuclear species

where, A = (*E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino) acetic acid; (*S,E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylidene-amino)propanoic acid; (*R*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzyl-

ideneamino)-3-methylbutanoic acid; B = tris(2-aminoethyl)amine (tren), Im = imidazolate ion. All synthesized imidazolate-bridged hetero-metallic binuclear complexes give satisfactory elemental analysis (Table 1). The Schiff base ligands were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and glycine, alanine and valine, respectively, in ethanol for 2–4 h (Scheme 2). The $H_2L-H_2L^2$ is diprotic ligand typically act as tridentate, planar chelate ligand coordinating through phenolic-O, azomethine-N and carboxylate-O atom. The proposed structures of the complexes **1-3** of $H_2L-H_2L^2$ was given in Scheme 3.

Magnetic moments :

The room temperature effective magnetic moments values (μ_{eff}) for the investigated hetero-binuclear com-

plexes are given in Table 1 along with their physical data. The observed room temperature magnetic moments of hetero-binuclear complexes $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ \mathbf{1}$; $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ \mathbf{2}$; $[(L^2)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ \mathbf{3}$ was around 1.75–1.79 B.M., in agreement with an unpaired one spin ($S = 1/2$) system.

Infrared spectral investigation :

Present complexes were characterized by FT-IR spectroscopy. The IR spectrum of the complexes was compared with those of free ligands ($H_2L-H_2L^2$) in order to determine the involvement of the coordination sites in the chelation. Analysis by FT-IR results in the absorption spectra in the infrared region and register bands or signals. IR spectrum of the $H_2L-H_2L^2$ ligands exhibited the most characteristic bands at 1635–1640 cm^{-1}

Scheme 3. The proposed structure of the complexes $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ \mathbf{1}$; $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ \mathbf{2}$; $[(L^2)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ \mathbf{3}$ of $H_2L-H_2L^2$.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data for binuclear imidazolate-bridged complexes **1-3**

Ligands and metal their complexes	Empirical formula (F.W.)	Colour	$\mu_{\text{eff.}}$ (B.M.)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :				
					Found (Calcd.)				
					C	H	N	Cu	Zn
H ₂ L	C ₉ H ₈ BrNO ₃ (F.W. = 258.07)	Red	–	90	41.89 (41.92)	3.12 (3.14)	5.43 (5.45)	–	–
H ₂ L ¹	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ BrNO ₃ (F.W. = 272.10)	Yellow	–	95	44.14 (44.17)	3.70 (3.72)	5.15 (5.18)	–	–
H ₂ L ²	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ BrNO ₃ (F.W. = 300.15)	Green	–	90	48.02 (48.05)	4.70 (4.72)	4.67 (4.69)	–	–
[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 1	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ BrCuN ₇ O ₆ Zn (F.W. = 598.29)	Blue	1.48	80	36.13 (36.16)	4.55 (4.57)	16.39 (16.42)	10.62 (10.65)	10.93 (10.65)
[(L ¹)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 2	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ BrCuN ₇ O ₆ Zn (F.W. = 613.33)	Green	1.75	75	34.21 (34.24)	4.93 (4.95)	15.99 (16.10)	10.36 (10.39)	10.66 (10.69)
[(L ²)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 3	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ BrCuN ₇ O ₆ Zn (F.W. = 641.38)	Green	1.89	85	39.33 (39.36)	5.34 (5.36)	15.29 (15.32)	9.91 (9.94)	10.20 (10.23)

v(azomethine-N), 3150–3240 cm⁻¹ v(phenolic-OH), and 1390–1470 cm⁻¹ v(carboxylate-O atom).

The formation of Schiff bases, (*E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)acetic acid; (*S,E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)propionic acid; (*R*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)-3-methylbutanoic acid, was noted from the absence of C=O and NH₂ peaks in the ligands (Scheme 2). A strong band observed at *ca.* 1215–1330 cm⁻¹ was assigned to coordination through phenolic OH. The bands with a maximum of 3025–3040 cm⁻¹ (ν_{N-H}), characteristics for imidazole disappeared in the spectra of the metal complexes, indicating the presence of the imidazolate ion. The perchlorate ion shows a *T_d* symmetry, which is characteristics for the free ion, supporting that it does not take part in the coordination around the metal ions. The bands maximums of the deformation vibrations of the molecules do not change drastically, but their intensities increased. This fact indicates to the binuclear complexes, indicating also the formation of metal complexes with the suggestive structures^{20,21} (Scheme 3). The IR data of ligands and their corresponding binuclear metal complexes showed that the Schiff bases were coordinated to the metal ion in a tridentate manner (ONO donor sites).

Electron paramagnetic resonance studies :

X-band EPR spectra of hetero-binuclear complexes **1-3** were recorded in polycrystalline state and also in 100% DMSO at room temperature and at liquid nitrogen tem-

perature (77 K). The polycrystalline EPR spectra of complexes **1-3** shows a weak half field signals ($\Delta M_s = 2$) at RT and LNT. Basic spectral characteristics at both temperatures are same only better resolution was obtained at LNT. The spectra of hetero-binuclear complexes are characteristics of *S* = 1/2. The EPR parameters calculated from their respective spectra are given in Table 2. The EPR spectra of complexes **1-3** of H₂L-H₂L² was given in Fig. 1.

Interestingly, the EPR spectra of **1-3** are similar. For each complex spectral feature of RT and LNT was also similar. The *g* = 2 signals for these complexes was broad and nearly isotropic. This is suggestive of the presence of spin-spin interactions which may be only intermolecular type in case of hetero-binuclear complexes **1-3**. This type of signals ($\Delta M_s = 2$) was observed in the known hetero-binuclear bridged complexes²² and has been attributed to intermolecular spin-spin interactions arising due to solid effect²³. The EPR spectra of these complexes in frozen solution exhibit the usual line shape for mononuclear copper(II) complexes with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.03$, indicating the axial symmetry. The measured values of g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} for the complexes **1-3** was 2.207/2.012, 2.206/2.015, 2.205/2.013, respectively. The hyperfine coupling constant for the complexes **1-3** was 170G, 175G, and 180G, respectively. It should be pointed out that these values are quite close to that of Cu₂Zn₂SOD²⁴ ($g_{\parallel} = 2.271$, $g_{\perp} = 2.083$).

Table 2. EPR parameters (100% DMSO) for some imidazolate-bridged Cu^{II}-Zn^{II} complexes

Sr. No.	Complexes	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel} (G)	pH	Ref.
1.	[Cu,Zn-SOD]	2.31	–	152	7.0	4
2.	[(Cu-Im-Zn)L](ClO ₄) ₃	2.20	2.06	155	6.0–10.5	4
3.	[(trien)Cu-Im-Zn(trien)](ClO ₄) ₃ ·H ₂ O	2.21	–	174	9.6–10.3	22
4.	[(Dtma)Cu-Im-Zn(Dtma)](ClO ₄) ₃ ·H ₂ O	2.22	–	179	10.0–12.0	4
5.	[(dien)Cu-Im-Zn(dien)](ClO ₄) ₃	2.20	2.05	185	9.5–12.5	12
6.	[(glygly)Cu-Im-Zn(glygly)]Na	2.21	2.04	165	7.0–10.0	12
7.	[(glyala)Cu-Im-Zn(glyala)]Na	2.22	2.06	165	7.15–10.50	12
8.	[(glyval)Cu-Im-Zn(glyval)]Na	2.216	2.052	165	7.15–9.5	12
9.	[(dien)Cu-2MeIm-Zn(dien)](ClO ₄) ₃	2.201	2.048	190	7.1–10.0	12
10.	[(PMDT)Cu-Im-Zn(PMDT)](ClO ₄) ₂	2.222	2.03	170	7.01–1.5	12
11.	[(Tren)Cu-E-Im-Zn(Tren)](ClO ₄) ₃	2.209	2.012	115	5.5–10.5	12
12.	[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 1	2.208	2.017	170	6.50–10.50	This work
13.	[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 2	2.203	2.011	175	8.50–10.50	This work
14.	[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 3	2.205	2.013	180	> 11.00	This work

Fig. 1. EPR spectra in DMSO (3×10^{-3} M) at 77 K of imidazolate-bridged complexes of [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **1**, [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **2** and [(L²)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **3**.

Solution stability of [Cu, Zn (Im)]⁻ units :

The solution EPR spectra of [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **1**; [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **2**; [(L²)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **3**, in frozen 50% aq. DMSO solutions as a function of pH, have been recorded. The pH of the solution in the range 6.50 to 11.00 pH unit was adjusted using HClO₄ and NaOH solutions. The obtained EPR spectral data was given in Table 2. Attempts were made to study the species formed due to breaking of imidazolate bridged.

In the pH range 6.50–11.00, the complexes showed well resolved EPR features for the single binuclear species. This is indicative that the binuclear species was intact in this pH range. On lowering the pH (i.e. below 6.50) the presence of new peak features reflect the presence of at least four axially or nearly axially species in the solution, possibilities for which are given as : [(A)Cu-ImH]; [(B)Zn-OH₂]²⁺; [(A)Cu-OH₂] and [Cu(H₂O)₆]²⁺. The presence of aqua species [Cu(H₂O)₆]²⁺ was verified

by observing *g*_{||}, *g*_⊥ and *A*_{||} (G) (Table 2), which are quite close to those of [Cu(H₂O)₆]²⁺ in the same frozen solution²⁴. As the pH increases, the *A*_{||} values also increase to 170G, suggesting the formation of imidazolate-bridged binuclear species. In the pH range 6.50–11.00, there is no specific change in the EPR parameters and in EPR features. This is suggestive that the imidazolate-bridged is intact in this pH range.

Superoxide dismutase activity determination :

These complexes exhibit significant catalytic activity towards the dismutation of superoxide anion. The superoxide was generated from alkaline DMSO and SOD activity was evaluated by the NBT assay. The count fraction causing 50% inhibition of NBT reduction is called IC₅₀ concentration, equivalent to one unit of SOD activity (IC₅₀ values), together with the IC₅₀ values of native SOD are given in Table 4. The superoxide dismutase activity of complexes **1-3** of H₂L-H₂L² was given in Fig. 2.

Table 3. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity of some imidazolate-bridged binuclear complexes

Sr. No.	Imidazolate-bridged complexes	IC ₅₀ (μmol dm ⁻³)	Ref.
1.	[(dien)-Cu-Im-Zn-(tren)] ³⁺	69.1	11
2.	[(bipy)-Cu-Im-Zn-(tren)] ³⁺	43.0	11
3.	[bis(bipy)-Cu-Im-Zn-(tren)] ³⁺	56.5	11
4.	[(terpy)-Cu-Im-Zn-(tren)] ³⁺	111.1	11
5.	[(bipy)-Cu-Im-Zn-(bis(bipy))] ³⁺	49.7	11
6.	[bis(bipy)-Cu-Im-Zn-(bis(bipy))] ³⁺	58.5	11
7.	Native SOD	0.04	11
8.	[(tren)-Cu-E-Im-Zn-(tren)](ClO ₄) ₃	81	12
9.	[(PMDT)-Cu-Ox-Zn-(PMDT)](BPh ₄) ₂ ·2CH ₃ CN	205	12
10.	[(salval)-Cu-Im-Zn-(salval)]Na	22	12
11.	[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 1	42	This work
12.	[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 2	40	This work
13.	[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 3	35	This work

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of imidazolate-bridged binuclear complex [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **1** and [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]⁺ **2**

Complexes (mM)	Diameter of inhibition zone (in mm)			
	<i>Streptococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 1				
10	8	9	7	5
20	13	16	12	11
30	18	20	16	14
[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)] ⁺ 2				
10	6	8	5	3
20	11	14	10	8
30	15	18	14	13

Fig. 2. Superoxide dismutase activity of imidazolate-bridged complexes $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+$ **1**, $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+$ **2** and $[(L^2)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+$ **3**.

The observed SODs (IC_{50}) values of imidazolate-bridged binuclear complexes $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+$ **1**; $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+$ **2**; $[(L^2)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+$ **3** ($IC_{50} = 42 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **1**, $IC_{50} = 40 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **2**, $IC_{50} = 35 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **3**, respectively) was higher than the value exhibited by the native enzyme ($IC_{50} = 0.04 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$) on a molar base (note that the smaller the IC_{50} value, the higher the SOD activity). The SOD activity of present complexes in the increasing order $3 > 2 > 1$, where it appears that the inclusion of ONO donor ligands ($H_2L/H_2L^1/H_2L^2$) reduce the SOD activity. The observed IC_{50} values of the present complexes are comparable with the various reported values for the imidazolate-bridged binuclear complexes^{11,12}, but are less active than the native SOD. A strong ligand field may oppose the interaction of the copper with superoxide radicals, being unfavorable to the probable formation of intermediate copper superoxide adduct. In conclusion, the present imidazolate-bridged complexes of $H_2L-H_2L^2$ was appears to be a fairly good models for the copper(II) site of intact Cu_2,Zn_2 -SOD because these showed several structural and spectroscopic features similar to the active site of the enzyme.

Relationship to the biological system :

Many enzymes and proteins have copper at their active site, which play a key role in biology of many enzymes and proteins, which play a key role in biology. The copper containing enzymes and proteins constitute an important class of biologically active compounds/model compounds. The biological functions of copper proteins/enzymes include electro transfer, dioxygen transport, oxygenation, oxidation, reduction and disproportionation. The copper(II) is a useful paramagnetic probe of protein structure and therefore is an important to ascertain the nature of its amino acid, peptide and protein complexes. The present synthesized imidazolate-bridged complexes appears to be good models for the active site in $[Cu_2,Zn_2$ -SOD]. These complexes showed similar features in common with $[Cu_2,Zn_2$ -SOD] subunits. In particular, EPR, magnetic susceptibility measurement and SOD data (Table 3) are closed to proteins. As this article, herein we adds substantial data to the chemistry of $[Cu_2,Zn_2$ -SOD] models and is therefore, relevant to the biochemistry of this element.

Antibacterial activity against pathogens :

In the present investigation the antibacterial (antimi-

crobial) activity of synthesized binuclear complexes was studied. The antibacterial activity of imidazolate-bridged binuclear complexes was evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. These activities were determined at three concentrations i.e. 10, 20 and 30 mM of each compound in DMSO and result were compared with lower concentration of standard antibiotic (chloramphenicol). Each experiment was performed in triplicate. Complexes $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$ and $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 2$; have shown excellent antibacterial activity against *E. coli* comparable to that of *Streptococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

The susceptibility of certain strains of bacteria towards the present binuclear metal complexes was judged by measuring the size of inhibition diameter. They inhibited the bacterial growth up to 18–29% at 30 mM whereas others have poor antibacterial activity²⁵. These complexes show lower activity than the known antibiotic chloramphenicol with $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$ being more active than $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 2$. The antibacterial activity of $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$; $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 2$ and $[(L^2)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 3$ was graphically presented in Fig. 3 and results of these antibacterial assessments of complexes were shown in Table 4. It has been proved from data that complex $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$ was most effective which inhibit the growth of all tested bacteria and zone of inhibition was greater than *Streptococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Similar antibacterial results were reported by Tarafder *et al.*²⁶.

Antifungal activity :

The antifungal activities of copper(II) complexes were determined against two fungal strains viz. *Aspergillus sp.*, *Pencillium sp.*, *Trichoderma sp.* and *Microsporum audonii*. These species were isolated from infected organs of the host plants on potato dextrose agar (potato 250 g + dextrose 20 g + agar 20 g) medium. The cultures of the fungi were purified by single spore isolation technique. Different concentrations 10, 20 and 30 mg/mL of each compound in DMSO were prepared for testing against spore germination. A drop of the solution of each concentration was kept separately on glass slides. The conidia, fungal reproducing spores (~200) lifted with the help of an inoculating needle, were mixed in every drop of each

compound separately. Each treatment was replicated thrice and a parallel DMSO solvent control set was run concurrently on separate glass slides. All the slides were incubated in humid chambers at 25 ± 2 °C for 24 h. The zone of inhibition of these compounds against those fungi was recorded in Table 5. Antifungal screening data are graphically presented in Fig. 4. Similar trends were observed as in the case of bacteria.

The area of percent of inhibition of spore germination ($mg\ mL^{-1}$) is less in the concentration of 5 mM in both fungi and more in 15 mM concentration. It was noted that these complexes are more effective against *Penicillium sp.* than *Aspergillus sp.*, *Trichoderma sp.* and *Microsporum audonii*. It was noted that *Penicillium sp.* was highly susceptible against $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$. Another fungi *Aspergillus sp.*, *Trichoderma sp.* and *Microsporum audonii* showed least effectiveness against $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$; but comparatively more susceptible towards $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 2$. It is observed from these tests that metal chelates have a higher activity than

Fig. 3. Antibacterial activity of imidazolate-bridged complexes $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$, $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 2$ and $[(L^2)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 3$.

Table 5. Antifungal activity of imidazolate-bridged binuclear complex $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$ and $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 2$

Complexes (mM)	% Inhibition of spore germination (mg mL ⁻¹)			
	<i>Aspergillus sp.</i>	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	<i>Trichoderma sp.</i>	<i>Microsporium audonii</i>
$[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$				
10	8	11	7	6
20	15	18	13	11
30	20	23	17	15
$[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 2$				
10	7	9	6	4
20	13	16	10	8
30	19	21	16	14

Fig. 4. Antifungal activity of imidazolate-bridged complexes $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$, $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 2$ and $[(L^2)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 3$.

the free ligands ($H_2L-H_2L^2$). This would suggest that the chelation facilitates the activity of the metal complex to cross a cell membrane and can be explained by the basis of overtones concept²⁷ and Tweedy's chelation theory²⁸.

Conclusion

$[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 1$; $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 2$; $[(L^2)Cu-Im-Zn(tren)]^+ 3$, were synthesized and characterized by different physico-chemical and spectroscopic

techniques. In many copper proteins and enzymes, the imidazole ring is an essential metal binding site, and thus a wide variety of imidazole containing ligands have been investigated to mimic structural features of these biomolecules. The results obtained with the tridentate Schiff base ligands ($H_2L-H_2L^2$) and tris(2-aminoethyl)amine, showed that they are good models for active site in $[Cu_2, Zn_2-SOD]$, existing the characteristics distorted structure around the copper ion, as well as a marked SOD activity. A modulation of this activity can be supplied by small structural variations. Strong antiferromagnetic coupling was usually observed in these binuclear complexes 1-3. Additionally, binuclear compounds can be interesting catalysts for reaction of hydrogen peroxide, occurring via two electron transfer reaction.

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